

Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AP	Average Precision
AR	Average Recall
FN	False Negative
FP	False Positive
IoU	Intersection over Union
mAP	Mean Average Precision
MSE	Mean Squared Error
PSNR	Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SSIM	Structural Similarity Index
SUT	System Under Test
TP	True Positive